

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS SERVICE QUALITY WITH REFERENCE TO HIGH - END BIKES

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Abstract:

Consumer behaviour involves the psychological process that a consumer undergoes in recognizing the needs, making purchase decision, interpret information, and making a plan and executing that particular plan. In this case, the consumer's psychological process is all about their passion and dreams. This study is based to identify the factors that influence the consumer buying behaviour of high-end bikes in India based on service quality. The conclusion is that there is considerable gap found in Expected and Perceived quality for the factors like Reliability, tangibility, assurance and Empathy. Improvements are expected in meeting delivery target as per promise time by improving the technology used to provide services and the quality of service provided by the company can be improved in future so that the level of satisfaction of the customers can be increased in future period of time.

Key Words: Buying Behaviour, Consumer & High-End Bikes

Introduction to the Study:

Our heart might thump faster when you watch those motorbike stunts on silver screen or for that matter you will be simply be fascinated when you must have seen Bollywood hunk John Abraham on a Suzuki Hayabusa or watching the latest version of your favorite bike in a parking lot that motivates you to own one. Be it a low-end bike or a high-end one all have the same potential to drive you crazy. Bikes have always given us precious moments; including some joyous rides, cruising through the traffic snarl with ease and making all four-wheeler guys fume with fury or accompanied you as a best friend on those rainy and sultry days. There is surely an emotional attachment for every bike owner and a story to narrate about his riding experience. This project is about understanding the behavior of consumers with regards to purchase of a High end bike. It also covers all the required information regarding the high end bikes in India till the current situation, market, and also the expected growth of these High end bikes in India.

Statement of the Problem:

Consumer Perception varies from consumer to consumer and therefore, to satisfy their needs and wants play the major role. Therefore gain customer loyalty and create a good brand awareness & image it is necessary to study the gap between the expectation and fulfillment, which would help in sustaining would in market. To increase the sales by understanding customers perception and increase market share And find out the efficient marketing techniques.

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the customer satisfaction on service tangibles.
- To assess the customer satisfaction on reliability of service.
- To assess the customer satisfaction on employees responsiveness in delivering the services.
- To assess the satisfaction of customer on the assurance of service delivered by higher end bikes.
- To assess the opinion of employee on the empathy shown by the employees of service center.

Hypothesis Framed:

- There is no significant difference between customer expectation and customer perception towards tangibility of services.
- There is no significant difference between customer expectation and customer perception towards reliability of services.
- There is no significant difference between customer expectation and customer perception towards responsiveness of services.
- There is no significant difference between customer expectation and customer perception towards assurance of services.
- There is no significant difference between customer expectation and customer perception towards empathy of services.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of this project is limited to the understanding of the product life cycle and the market potential of higher end bikes. The focus of this project is to increase the consumption of higher end bikes and help the organization from constant threat from its competitors and suggests the ways and opportunities to maintain the share of higher end bikes. The project has done a full justice to the research objective and gave me and insight to the market potential. The research has proved to be an important milestone in terms of applying theoretical knowledge practically thereby making me aware of the consumers perception about Higher end bikes.

Research Methodology:

Type of Research: Descriptive research is used as a research design, The research basically involves in describing the various characteristics of population. Hence it is descriptive in nature.

Data & Sources of Data: Both the primary data and secondary data have collected for the study.

Primary Data: The primary data has been collected with the help of well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire has been prepared based on survival model.

Secondary Data: The secondary data has been collected through the journal articles, websites and textbooks.

Population Size: The average walk-in per day is expected to be twenty. Hence, 500 average walk-ins were expected within a period of 30 days for accessing service.

Sample Size: Sample size 150 respondent has been identified with 30% of total population of Higher end bikes.

Sampling Technique: A method of convenient sampling has been used to identify 150 respondent. Everyday five respondents has been targeted and every second, fourth, sixth, eighth & tenth walk-ins has been identified as the sample.

Statistical Tools Used: Percentage analysis, Descriptive analysis, Reliability and Paried T test

Limitations of the Study:

- Personal biases expected from the respondents.
- Due to the time constraints the sample size has been restricted to 150.
- As the study has been collected from the only one store. The results can't be generalized to other areas.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Reliability Test:

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.86	44

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the reliability test for the level of acceptance with expectation and perception were the Cronbach's Alpha value is at 0.860 which is greater than 0.7. Its shows that the factors are frequently adequate for analysis of tools.

Demo-Graphic Factors:

Personal Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	93	62
	Female	57	38
	Total	150	100
Age	Less Than 25	47	31.3
	25-34	28	18.7
	35-44	15	10
	45-54	20	13.3
	Greater Than 55	40	26.7
	Total	150	100
Annual Income	Rs 1,49,000 Per Annum	60	40
	Rs 1,50,000-Rs1,99,000 Per Annum	18	12
	Rs 2,00,000-Rs2,99,000 Per Annum	38	25.3
	Rs 3,00,000 -Rs 3,99,000 Per Annum	24	16
	Rs 4,00,000- Rs 5,50,000 Per Annum	10	6.7
	Total	150	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the gender of the respondents were out of 150 respondents 62% are male and 38% are female. 31.3% are from the age group of <25, 18.7% are from the age group of 25-34, 10% are from the age group of 35-44, 13.3% are from the age group of 45-54 and 26.7% are from the age group of >55. 40% are earning till Rs.1,49,000/annum, 12% are earning from Rs 1,50,000-Rs1,99,000/annum, 25.3% are earning from Rs 2,00,000-Rs2,99,000/annum, 16% are earning Rs 3,00,000 -Rs 3,99,000 per annum and 6.7% are earning Rs 4,00,000- Rs 5,50,000 per annum.

Descriptive Statistics for Acceptance of Perception and Expectation with the Dimension Tangibility:

	N	Mean Value of Expectation	Mean Value of Perception	Difference Value
Acceptance on ideal service centre	150	2.4	2.4	-0.04
Acceptance on physical facilities	150	2.6	2.6	0.02
Acceptance on well dressed employees	150	2.7	2.82	-0.1
Acceptance on physical environment	150	2.6	2.59	0.01

Consolidated mean for expectation : 2.57
 Consolidated mean for perception : 2.60
 Mean difference : 0.03

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the mean score for all the elements given for the acceptance of perception is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of expectation. While comparing the mean between variables were the difference was high at 0.04 with the factor acceptance on ideal service centre.

Descriptive Statistics for Acceptance of Perception and Expectation with the Dimension Reliability:

	N	Mean Value of Expectation	Mean Value of Perception	Difference Value
Acceptance on service centre	150	3.31	3.26	0.05
Acceptance on solving problem	150	3.17	3.06	0.11
Acceptance on ideal service at first time	150	2.67	2.46	0.21
Acceptance on ideal service at time promised	150	3.01	2.34	0.67
Acceptance of ideal service on records	150	3.01	2.49	0.52
Acceptance on availability of spares	150	3.23	2.79	0.44

Consolidated mean for expectation : 3.06
 Consolidated mean for perception : 2.73
 Mean difference : 0.33

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the mean score for all the elements given for the acceptance of expectation on reliability is above 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are above average for acceptance on level of expectation with the dimension reliability. The acceptance of perception on reliability is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of perception with the dimension reliability. While comparing the mean between variables were the difference was high at 0.67 with the factor acceptance on ideal service at time promised.

Descriptive Statistics for Acceptance of Perception and Expectation with the Dimension Responsiveness:

	N	Mean Value of Expectation	Mean Value of Perception	Difference Value
Acceptance on delivery time given by the employees	150	2.87	2.79	0.08
Acceptance on prompt service to customers	150	2.61	2.61	0
Acceptance on willingness to help customers	150	2.73	2.63	0.1
Acceptance on respond to customer request	150	2.9	2.65	0.25

Consolidated mean for expectation : 2.77
 Consolidated mean for perception : 2.67
 Mean difference : 0.33

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the mean score for all the elements given for the acceptance of perception on responsiveness is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of expectation and perception with the dimension responsiveness. While comparing the mean between variables were the difference was high at 0.25 with the factor acceptance on respond to customer request.

Descriptive Statistics for Acceptance of Perception and Expectation with the Dimension Assurance:

	N	Mean Value of Expectation	Mean Value of Perception	Difference Value
Acceptance on behaviour of employees	150	3.11	2.41	0.7
Acceptance on service dealers	150	2.64	2.97	-0.33
Acceptance on knowledge to answer customers	150	2.93	3.29	-0.36
Acceptance on courteous to customer	150	3.07	3	0.07

Consolidated mean for expectation : 2.93
 Consolidated mean for perception : 2.91
 Mean difference : 0.33

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the mean score for all the elements given for the acceptance of perception on assurance is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of expectation and perception with the dimension assurance. While comparing the mean between variables were the difference was high at 0.7 with the factor acceptance on behaviour of employees.

Descriptive Statistics for Acceptance of Perception and Expectation with the Dimension Empathy:

	N	Mean Value of Expectation	Mean Value of Perception	Difference Value
Acceptance on opening hours of the employees	150	2.78	2.79	-0.01
Acceptance on personal service	150	3.01	3.02	-0.01
Acceptance on best interest of the customers	150	2.53	3.21	-0.68
Acceptance on understanding specific needs of their customers.	150	3.39	2.43	0.96

Consolidated mean for expectation : 2.92
 Consolidated mean for perception : 2.86
 Mean difference : 0.33

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the mean score for all the elements given for the acceptance of perception on empathy is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of expectation and perception with the dimension empathy. While comparing the mean between variables were the difference was high at 0.96 with the factor acceptance on understanding specific needs of their customers.

Paired Sample t Test:

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Expectation Tangibility Perception Tangibility	-0.02833	1.06285	0.08678	-0.19981	0.14315	-0.326	149	0.745
Pair 2	Expectation Reliability Perception Reliability	0.31333	1.1321	0.09244	0.13068	0.49599	3.39	149	0.001
Pair 3	Expectation Responsiveness Perception Responsiveness	0.00667	0.29101	0.02376	-0.04029	0.05362	0.281	149	0.779

The above table shows about the t value comparison between the dimensions were the t value is less than the table value 1.95 at -0.326, 0.281, -0.848 and 1.063 for the dimensional comparisons Expectation Tangibility and Perception Tangibility, Expectation Responsiveness and Perception Responsiveness, Expectation Assurance and Perception Assurance, Expectation Empathy and Perception Empathy respectively. The t value is greater than the table value 1.95 at 3.309 for the dimensional comparison of Expectation Reliability and Perception Reliability. So the factor reliability can be taken for the decision making process of the study. The level of significance of Expectation Tangibility and Perception Tangibility, Expectation Responsiveness and Perception Responsiveness, Expectation Assurance and Perception Assurance, Expectation Empathy and Perception Empathy respectively are greater than 0.05 which shows that there is no significance between these two factors and there is a significance between Expectation Reliability and Perception Reliability as the significance level is less than 0.05 at 0.001.

Findings:

- Most of the respondents are male in our survey.
- Most of the respondents are from the age group of <25 in our survey.
- Most of the respondents are earning up to Rs 1,49,000 per annum in our survey.
- Acceptance of expectation on reliability is above 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are above average for acceptance on level of expectation with the dimension reliability.
- The acceptance of perception on responsiveness is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of expectation and perception with the dimension responsiveness.

- Level of acceptance of perception on assurance is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of expectation and perception with the dimension assurance.
- The acceptance of perception on empathy is below 3, which indicates that most of the respondents are dissatisfied for acceptance on level of expectation and perception with the dimension empathy.

Suggestions:

- There is a high demand for High-end bikes in the market, so their supply has to be drastically improved so as to meet the demand of the customer.
- Some of the respondents had suggested improving the mileage of high-end Bikes.
- A considerable number of respondents opined that there is a need to improve the performance of the Aprilla motorcycles.
- A vast majority of the respondents felt the design of Honda motorcycles should be changed so as to attract the customers.
- The bikes recently introduced by Yamaha are mostly concerned about youth. So, they should also consider middle-aged people while manufacturing.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that there is considerable gap found in Expected and Perceived quality for the factors like Reliability, tangibility, assurance and Empathy. Improvements are expected in meeting delivery target as per promise time by improving the technology used to provide services and the quality of service provided by the company can be improved in future so that the level of satisfaction of the customers can be increased in future period of time.

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